

Studies on Tartrate Complex of Cobalt (II)

K. K. Tripathy and R. K. Patnaik

Tartrate complex of Cobalt (II) has been studied by *pH* titration and conductometric measurement methods. Cobalt reacts with tartaric acid to form a neutral complexes C at low *pH* with the liberation of two protons. The neutral complex C then dissociates to complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} in two steps at higher *pH* range. The equilibrium constant of the reactions $Co^{2+} + H_2T \rightleftharpoons C + 2H^+$, $C \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$, $C_1^- \rightleftharpoons C_2^{2-} + H^+$, $Co^{2+} + T^{2-} \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$ and $Co^{2+} + HT^- \rightleftharpoons C + H^+$ are determined and found to be 8.28×10^{-6} , 3.43×10^{-8} , 1.32×10^{-10} , 3.31×10^{-6} and 4.15×10^{-2} respectively.

The complex formation between Cobalt(II) ion and tartaric acid has been studied by different workers employing spectrophotometric¹, ion exchange², chromatographic³ and potentiometric⁴ measurement methods.

Shin Suzuki² employing ion-exchange method reported the average ionisation constant at 25° for the reaction

$$K = [CoC_4H_4O_6][H^+]^2/[Co^{2+}][C_4H_6O_6] \quad \text{to be } 2.5 \times 10^{-9}.$$

Chin-Kuang Wu and Kuang-Hsien Hsu⁵ reported the instability constants *pK* and *pK'* for cobalt tartrate complex to be equal to 2.06 and 0.49 respectively where $K = (M)(L)/(ML)$ and $K' = (M)(HL)/(MHL)$, M and L representing the metal and the tartrate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Five *pH* and three conductometric titrations were performed at $32^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ the details of which are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1
pH titrations

Experiment	Contents in g. mole	Total Volume	Titrated against	Results
1. A Tartaric Acid	1.5×10^{-3}	100 ml.	M/10 Sodium Hydroxide	Fig. 1, Curve A
Sodium Perchlorate	1.0×10^{-2}			
Cobalt Nitrate	9.924×10^{-4}			
B Tartaric Acid	1.5×10^{-3}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
Sodium Perchlorate	1.0×10^{-2}			

1. M. Bobtelsky and C. Heitner, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1951, 494.
2. Shin Suzuki, *Science Repts. Research Institute, Tohoku Univ.* 1953, Ser A5, 311.
3. Eric John Sing and A. K. Dey, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1959, 165, 81.
4. E. Campi, G. Ostacoli, M. Meirone, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)* 1964, 54(6), 639.
5. Chin-Kuang Wu and Kuang-Hsu, *Chemical Abstracts*, 1960, 54, (4118b).

TABLE 1—Contd

Experiment	Contents in g. mole	Total Volume	Titrated against	Results	
2. A	Tartaric Acid Sodium Perchlorate	5.5×10^{-3} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	1.032 M/2 Sodium Hydroxide	Fig. 2, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Tartaric Acid Sodium Perchlorate	9.924×10^{-4} 5.5×10^{-3} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
3. A	Sodium Perchlorate	1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	M/10 Sodium Bitartrate	Fig. 3, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Sodium Perchlorate	9.924×10^{-4} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
4. A	Sodium Perchlorate	1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	M/10 Sodium Tartrate	Fig. 4, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Sodium Perchlorate	9.924×10^{-4} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
5. A	Sodium Tartrate Sodium Perchlorate	5.0×10^{-3} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	M/10 Sodium Hydroxide	Fig. 5, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Sodium Tartrate Sodium Perchlorate	9.924×10^{-4} 5.0×10^{-3} 1.0×10^{-2}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
<i>Conductometric Titrations</i>					
6. A	Tartaric Acid	1.25×10^{-3}	232.5 ml.	M/10 Sodium Hydroxide	Fig. 6, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Tartaric Acid	2.0×10^{-4} 1.25×10^{-3}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
7. A	Sodium Tartrate	5.0×10^{-4}	160 ml.	-do-	Fig. 7, Curve A
B	Cobalt Nitrate Sodium Tartrate	1.0×10^{-4} 5.0×10^{-4}	-do-	-do-	-do- Curve B
8.	Concentration of Cobalt Nitrate — Concentration of Sodium Tartrate — Total concentration	0.01M 0.01M — 0.1 M	Fig. 8.

All chemicals used were of BDH (Analar) grade. Double distilled water was used to prepare the solutions and cobalt was estimated by precipitation as tetrapyrindine cobalt dithiocyanate complex.

DISCUSSION

In experiment 1 (Fig. 1) where the metal to ligand ratio is approximately 1 : 1.5, a precipitate was formed around pH 7.0. The precipitate however was soluble beyond pH 11.0 during the pH titration. The compound on being isolated and analysed showed the presence of tartrate ion and contained 29.06% of cobalt. The compound can therefore be

assumed to be cobalt tartrate ($\text{CoC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$, % cobalt reqd. 28.5). The magnetic susceptibility measurement showed the μ_{eff} value to be 5.06 B.M. at 30° which is in agreement with the

FIG. 1

observations made by Ranadae and Subba Rao⁶. The compound did not also liberate iodine from potassium iodide which confirms that the oxidation state of cobalt has not undergone any change. The precipitation however was avoided in experiment 2 (Fig. 2) by maintaining a higher metal to ligand ratio (1 : 5.5 approximately).

FIG. 2.

6. A. C. Ranadae and V. V. Subba Rao, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4(1), 42.

The reaction between cobalt ion and tartaric acid in experiments 1 and 2 may be represented by

$$K = \frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Co}^{2+}][\text{H}_2\text{T}]} \quad \dots (1.1)$$

All calculations pertaining to the determination of K , K_1 and K_2 were made as discussed in the paper entitled Tartrate Complex of Manganese(II)⁷. The value of n was found to exceed 2 and 3 at and above $p\text{H}$ 5.8 and 8.5 respectively. The formation of complex C, therefore, is not complete below $p\text{H}$ 5.8. Assuming the value of $n = 2$, $[\text{C}]$, $[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{T}]$ were calculated below $p\text{H}$ 5.8 from experiment 1 and K was calculated by equation (1.1). The values are recorded in Table 2, the mean value thus obtained being 8.28×10^{-8} .

In the $p\text{H}$ ranges 5.8 to 8.5 the reaction taking place can be represented as

and

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} \quad \dots (2.1)$$

and reaction taking place in the $p\text{H}$ range 8.5 and above (experiment 2 only) can be represented as

and

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_1^-]} \quad \dots (3.1)$$

K_1 was calculated from experiment 1 by equation (2.1). The values are recorded in Table 2, the mean value thus obtained being 3.43×10^{-8} .

It was not possible to calculate the values of n beyond $p\text{H}$ 6.8 from experiment 1 since the precipitation starts around $p\text{H}$ 7.0. Since the values of K and K_1 obtained from experiment 2 are in agreement with those obtained from experiment 1, the K_2 values were calculated from experiment 2 by equation (3.1). The values are recorded in Table 3, the mean value thus obtained being 1.32×10^{-10} .

TABLE 2

Determination of K and K_1 from experiment 1

$p\text{H}$	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3$	$-\Delta[\text{T}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \times 10^3$	a/b	n	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Co}^{2+}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{H}_2\text{T}] \times 10^5$	$K \times 10^6$	$K_1 \times 10^6$
3.6	1.43	0.21	8.312	1.030	1.228	1.696	6.616	165.10	9.800	—
4.0	1.33	0.21	8.042	1.337	1.537	2.430	5.612	49.63	8.722	—
4.4	0.88	0.12	7.850	1.613	1.750	2.774	5.076	11.90	7.281	—
5.0	0.31	0.05	7.729	1.872	1.924	3.153	4.680	0.98	7.300	—
6.0	0.24	0.03	7.668	1.987	2.0251	—	—	—	—	2.571
6.4	0.54	0.08	7.635	1.995	2.0866	—	—	—	—	3.777
6.8	1.19	0.17	7.565	1.997	2.1991	—	—	—	—	3.941

TABLE 3

Determination of K, K₁ and K₂ from experiment 2

pH	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3$	$-\Delta[\text{T}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \times 10^3$	a/b	n	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Co}^{2+}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{H}_2\text{T}] \times 10^3$	K $\times 10^3$	K ₁ $\times 10^3$	K ₂ $\times 10^{10}$
3.4	3.29	0.36	8.853	0.877	1.284	3.211	5.642	10.81	8.345	—	—
4.0	3.05	0.33	8.496	1.337	1.748	5.265	3.231	2.135	7.633	—	—
4.4	2.02	0.20	8.337	1.613	1.894	6.053	2.284	0.5246	8.007	—	—
6.0	0.41	0.06	8.204	1.986	2.0505	—	—	—	—	5.321	—
6.8	1.65	0.19	8.175	1.997	2.2452	—	—	—	—	5.148	—
8.0	6.00	0.63	8.089	2.000	2.8974	—	—	—	—	8.748	—
8.5	6.93	0.73	8.069	2.000	3.040	—	—	—	—	—	1.317
9.0	7.54	0.79	8.056	2.000	3.132	—	—	—	—	—	1.521
9.4	8.12	0.85	8.042	2.000	3.221	—	—	—	—	—	1.129

In experiment 3 (Fig. 3) the pH decreases in the beginning and finally remains almost constant. Since the pH during the experiment remained below 5.8 (the pH below which

FIG. 3

complex C was formed in experiments 1 and 2) the reaction taking place here can be written as

and

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Co}^{2+}][\text{HT}^-]} \quad \dots (4.1)$$

Thus we have

$$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2] = [\text{Co}^{2+}] + [\text{C}] \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{H}^+] + [\text{H}_2\text{T}] - [\text{T}^{2-}] \quad \dots (6)$$

Hence

$$[\text{T}] = \text{Total tartrate} = [\text{H}_2\text{T}] + [\text{HT}^-] + [\text{T}^{2-}] + [\text{C}] \quad \dots (7)$$

and

$$[\text{T}] = [\text{H}^+] + r[\text{HT}^-] \quad \dots (8)$$

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{T}] - p[\text{HT}^-] \quad \dots (9)$$

where $r = 1 + \{2[\text{H}^+]/k_1\}$, and $p = 1 + \{[\text{H}^+]/k_1\} + \{[k_2/[\text{H}^+]]\}$

K_3 was then calculated according to equation (4.1). The values are recorded in Table 4, the mean value being 4.15×10^{-2} .

TABLE 4

Determination of K_3 from experiment 5

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[Co(NO ₃) ₂] $\times 10^3$	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[C] $\times 10^3$	[Co ²⁺] $\times 10^3$	K_3 $\times 10^2$
3.30	2.913	9.636	1.263	0.902	8.734	4.104
3.27	4.762	9.452	2.136	1.309	8.143	4.039
3.25	6.542	9.274	2.956	1.710	7.564	4.300

In experiment 4 (Fig. 4) the pH decreases gradually in the beginning, then remains almost constant and finally increases with increasing addition of sodium tartrate. The reaction taking place can be represented as

and

$$K_4 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Co}^{2+}][\text{T}^{2-}]} \quad \dots (10.1)$$

FIG. 4 .

The proton thus liberated is partly removed by C_1^- as a result of which the neutral complex is formed according to the equation $\text{C}_1^- + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{C}$. The pH remains almost constant for a certain range mainly due to the formation of C and its dissociation to C_1^- and H^+ and finally rises due to the addition of further amount of sodium tartrate. Beyond the 1:1 equivalence point we therefore have the reaction $\text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_1^- + \text{H}^+$ and it can be shown that

$$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] \quad \dots (11)$$

$$[\text{T}] - [\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2] = p[\text{HT}^-] \quad \dots (12)$$

and

$$[\text{C}_1^-] = r[\text{HT}^-] + [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots (13)$$

K_1 was then calculated by equation (2.1). The values are recorded in Table 5, the mean value being 2.97×10^{-8} which is in agreement with the values obtained in experiments 1 and 2.

TABLE 5

Determination of K_1 from experiment 4

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[Co(NO ₃) ₂] $\times 10^3$	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C] $\times 10^3$	K_1 $\times 10^8$
5.81	13.79	8.555	11.49	11.68	8.438	2.145
5.85	16.66	8.269	16.84	17.03	8.099	2.970
5.90	20.64	7.875	22.88	23.05	7.645	3.796

Below 1 : 1 equivalence point the formation of the complex is not complete and we have therefore

$$[T] = p[HT^-] + q[C_1^-] \quad \dots (14)$$

where $q = 1 + \{[H^+]/K_1\}$ so that K_4 was calculated according to the equation (10.1). The values are recorded in Table 6, the mean value being 3.31×10^{-6} .

TABLE 6

Determination of K_4 from experiment 4

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[Co(NO ₃) ₂] $\times 10^3$	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C] $\times 10^3$	[T ²⁻] $\times 10^3$	[Co ²⁺] $\times 10^3$	K_4 $\times 10^6$
6.0	1.961	9.729	1.927	2.031	0.592	1.329	9.117	1.676
5.9	2.913	9.636	3.063	3.196	1.173	1.679	8.431	2.843
5.8	4.762	9.452	5.101	5.275	2.437	2.221	6.962	5.406

In experiment 5 (Fig. 5) the metal to ligand ratio is approximately 1 : 5 so that the formation of the complex can be assumed to be complete. Since the reactions $C \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$

FIG. 5.

and $C_1^- \rightleftharpoons C_2^{2-} + H^+$ are taking place at pH values 5.8 and 8.5 respectively (experiment 1 and 2) the same can be assumed to be taking place in this experiment. The values of K_1

and K_2 which represent the equilibrium constant for the above reactions respectively were determined by exactly similar method as discussed in case of manganese tartrate complex⁷. The values of K_1 and K_2 are recorded in Table 7 and Table 8, the mean values thus obtained being 6.41×10^{-8} and 1.65×10^{-10} respectively. The values are in agreement with those obtained in experiments 1 and 2.

TABLE 7

Determination of K_1 from experiment 5

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[Co(NO ₃) ₂] $\times 10^3$	[NaOH] $\times 10^3$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[C] $\times 10^3$	K_1 $\times 10^8$
6.5	49.41	9.806	1.186	1.367	8.439	5.112
6.8	48.73	9.672	2.534	2.624	7.048	5.900
7.1	47.62	9.452	4.762	4.806	4.646	8.215

TABLE 8

Determination of K_2 from experiment 5

pH	[NaOH] $\times 10^3$	[Co(NO ₃) ₂] $\times 10^3$	[C ₂ ²⁻] $\times 10^3$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^3$	K_2 $\times 10^{10}$
9.0	10.40	8.894	1.506	7.388	2.038
9.2	10.72	8.861	1.859	7.002	1.675
9.5	11.27	8.806	2.464	6.342	1.228

FIG 6.

It can be shown that $K_4 \times k_1 \times k_2 / K_1 = K$. By substituting the values of K_4 , k_1 and k_2 , the value of K is found out to be 7.32×10^{-6} which is in agreement with the mean value obtained in experiment 1 (8.28×10^{-6}). It can also be shown that $K_3 \times k_1 = K$ and substituting the values of K_3 and k_1 the value obtained for K is 4.56×10^{-5} which is fairly in agreement with the mean value obtained in experiment 1 (0.828×10^{-5}).

FIG 7 .

Conductometric titrations: In experiment 6 (Fig. 6, Curve B) the decrease in conductance and subsequent breaks obtained at P_1 and P_2 indicate the formation of complexes

FIG. 8

C, C_1^- and C_2^{2-} respectively. The sharp rise in conductance beyond the point P_3 is due to the addition of excess sodium hydroxide.

In experiment 7 (Fig. 7, Curve B) the breaks at P_1 and P_2 correspond to the addition of one and two equivalents of sodium hydroxide per gm. atom of cobalt respectively. This indicates the neutralisation of the first and second proton released by the dissociation of the neutral complex C. The existence of the complexes C, C_1^- and C_2^{2-} is thus confirmed.

In experiment 8 (Fig. 8) the peak corresponding to the value of 0.5 for the ratio $[Co^{2+}]/[Co^{2+}]+[T^{2-}]$ obtained by Job's method further confirms the formation of 1:1 complex.

Department of Chemistry,
Regional Engineering College,
Rourkela-8 (Orissa).

Received November 6, 1967,
Revised MSS received September 6, 1969.